

LIBRARY

Opportunities for Data Exchange

THE ODE PROJECT / LIBRARIES

Opportunities for Data Sharing

There is a growing consensus in science, and society generally, that primary research data resulting from publicly funded research should be shared widely so that the maximum benefits can be gained from the investment. There are common barriers and some reluctance, but also powerful drivers and benefits related to putting this general principle into practice.

Why should you as a librarian care about data sharing?

As a librarian you are known for your expertise in enabling access to information resources for researchers. You can further expand and utilise your knowledge of adding value to and preservation of research outputs to support researchers with various services and tools to facilitate data exchange.

Do you know about others' views?

The EU FP7-funded ODE project has collected views from numerous individuals – representative of all stakeholder groups involved – on the opportunities for data exchange. These views were analysed and consolidated in order to inform each group about each others' views and possible future activities.

To obtain more results from our research, please visit:

www.ode-project.eu/ode-outputs

What ODE has learned:

Co-operation between libraries, publishers and data centres is important when developing common structures and services. Examples include data publication, quality assurance, peer review, citation, linking and persistent identifiers.

Data centres (providing services similar to those of libraries) and research funders pointed out the importance of seeking synergies with other service providers to offer added-value services to researchers and of working in close collaboration with the research community to develop these.

Data owners and producers are also supportive of libraries offering support and tools for effective data management, sharing and re-use.

What you and your organization can do:

Data librarianship is becoming more and more relevant in the field of research data management. Therefore, it is crucial to work as a community to develop and provide professional training opportunities.

Furthermore, you can combine your knowledge and skills with those of both data users and producers. They will need your guidance for strategic data management, as well as training on retrieval of data sets and the usage of persistent identifiers. Working closely together with the research community will help you to provide them with services tailored to their needs.

Your advocacy and promotion of the benefits of data sharing to your researchers will encourage them to share.

Together with publishers and data centres, you can work on developing an incentive system which gives credit and recognition for shared data. Promote this by giving your researchers clear instructions and advice on how to cite data.

Data is the new gold.

"We have a huge goldmine... Let's start mining it."

Neelie Kroes, Vice-President of the European Commission responsible for the Digital Agenda
<http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/11/872&type=HTML>

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